

NEW ADDITIONS TO THE *MANZONIA* FAUNA OF THE CANARY ISLANDS (GASTROPODA: RISSOIDAE)

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Introduction:

The Macaronesian species of the genus *Manzonia* were recently treated by MOOLENBEEK & FABER (1987a, b, c) and ROLÁN (1987). It became clear that due to radiation on these east Atlantic Islands at least 13 taxa could develop.

Nearly all islands were covered by their research and thousands of shells were studied. In 1989 we could collect samples on some of the smaller Canary Islands of which we had seen only minor quantities. In algaewashings from El Hierro, we found a smooth *Manzonia* species which at first sight looked like a beached *M. manzoniana* (ROLÁN, 1987). However, when finding live specimens, it became evident that it represented an unknown species, living sympatric with *M. manzoniana*. It is described below. Also the first record of *M. vigoensis* (ROLÁN, 1983) from the Canary Islands is mentioned.

Systematic part

Manzonia heroensis sp. nov.

(Figs. 1-2, 4-5)

Description of holotype: Shell very small, length 1.9 mm, width 1.0 mm, glossy, smooth, semitransparent, vitreous (figs. 1-2). Protoconch dome-shaped, smooth about one convex whorl, a little intorted. Teleconch of 3 smooth convex whorls with only some irregular growth lines, especially prominent near aperture. Just below suture a subsutural ridge. Basal groove rather well developed. Aperture subcircular, peristome entire and simple. Outerlip strongly opisthocline. Operculum brown, horny. Anatomy not studied.

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Etymology: Named after the island El Hierro, which was named "Hero" in mediaeval times by the original inhabitants the Guanches. As far as we know now this species seems to be endemic in the sea around El Hierro.

Type specimens: Holotype length 1.9 mm, width 1.0 mm (ZMA Moll. 3.90.018). From the locality 34 paratypes (ZMA Moll. 3.90.019) which will also be distributed to the Museo Insular de Ciencias Naturales, Tenerife and to Dr. E. ROLÁN (Vigo).

Type locality: Canary Islands, El Hierro, Tamadusta harbour, 3-5 m, in algae (Sta. 89/49), June, 1989. leg. R.G. MOOLENBEEK & L. DUIVEMAN.

Other Material studied: El Hierro; Pozo de las Calcosas, tidal pools. Sta. 89/39, 6 specimens; Restinga, harbour 2-3 m, sta. 89/47, 6 specimens; Puerto de la Estaca, 2-10 m, Sta. 89/50, 12 specimens. All June 1989 leg. R.G. MOOLENBEEK & L. DUIVEMAN.

Variability: This species shows little variation in size, ranging from 1.7-2.2 mm. More slender specimens have more convex whorls too.

Discussion: We already mentioned in the introduction the close resemblance to *M. manzoniana* (ROLÁN, 1987). However, it differs in lacking microsculpture on the

protoconch and teleoconch. Also the duplicated peristome lacks, which convinced us that this character is not always of value for generic placement. It is different from the genus *Onoba* by having a well-developed basal groove. This groove also lacks in *Peringiella nitida*, a species which can be confused at first sight with the new species. Another resembling species is *Hyala vitrea* (MONTAGU, 1803). However, this species is larger (2.5-3mm), more fragile, and has more convex whorls with a typical irravadiid-like protoconch.

Manzonia (Moniziella) vigoensis (ROLÁN, 1983)

(Fig. 3)

This rare species was only known from the Atlantic coast of the Iberian Peninsula. The finding of one fresh specimen on El Hierro (Puerto de las Estaca, 2-10m, June 1989) was an unexpected surprise and is a considerable range extension. In a dredge sample from the National Natuurhistorisch Museum Leiden (RMNH) we found another specimen from the CANCAP IV Expedition, Sta. 4.048, South of Lanzarote, 28°48'N-13°46'W, 215-325 m, 17 May 1980.

ABSTRACT

Manzonia heroensis sp. nov. of the family Rissoidae is an endemic species from the island El Hierro, Canary Islands. *M. vigoensis* (ROLÁN, 1983) is recorded for the first time from the Canary Islands.

Key words: Rissoidae, *Manzonia*, El Hierro, Canary Islands.

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